

LLM Persuasiveness Evaluation: A Structured Review of Automated Methods

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Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) are becoming increasingly capable of persuading and even manipulating humans, with the potential to shape beliefs, behaviour, and public discourse at scale. These capabilities have been highlighted as malicious-use risks in the International AI Safety Report (Bengio et al. 2025), and increasingly impactful AI regulations now aim to assess and mitigate them while preserving potential benefits. It is therefore critical that LLM persuasiveness and related capabilities are thoroughly evaluated and well understood. To date, dozens of empirical studies have assessed LLM persuasion using human participants. Such evaluations are costly, logistically complex, hard to scale, and constrained by ethical challenges, making them impractical for the systematic evaluation of rapidly evolving LLMs. As an alternative, a growing body of work has proposed fully automated evaluation approaches that require no human involvement. In this structured review, we provide a systematic taxonomy of such automated approaches across 30 methods from 27 papers, examine how they are validated against human judgement, and discuss their limitations and risks. We find the field fragmented, and human validation limited and inconsistent: alignment with human judgement is strong for argument assessment but mixed for belief and behavioural change metrics, raising concerns about reliance on synthetic proxies for safety-critical assessment. Despite these limitations, automated methods offer value beyond fully replacing human studies, for applications such as preliminary screening and high-risk scenario testing. We conclude by outlining directions for future research in this fast-moving field, and accompany the review with a living open-access resource hub.

Keywords: Large Language Models, evaluation, persuasion, manipulation

1 Introduction

Persuasion is central to human interaction across social, commercial, and public spheres, shaping processes as diverse as political campaigning, marketing, health communication, and public deliberation (Bassi et al. 2024). In the digital era, algorithmic curation, personalised content delivery, and persuasive system design have made persuasion increasingly computational and data-driven (Fogg 2003; Bassi et al. 2024). This shift has culminated in the emergence of “synthetic persuasion”: LLMs acting as interactive agents that can tailor arguments, mimic affect, and adapt across multi-turn dialogue (Bozdag et al. 2026; Breum et al. 2024; Doudkin et al. 2025). Whereas persuasion was previously either personalised (one-on-one) or scalable (mass media), LLMs enable both simultaneously, delivering automated, interactive, and hyper-personalised influence at scale.

Empirical evidence indicates that frontier LLMs are becoming increasingly persuasive (Rogiers et al. 2024). Early studies in 2024 showed that LLM persuasive abilities were rapidly approaching human performance across a range of controlled settings (Ma et al. 2025; Salvi et al. 2025; Durmus et al. 2024), and by 2025 several studies documented persuasion parity or even superiority relative to humans (Meguellati et al. 2025; Becker et al. 2025; Li et al. 2025; Maier et al. 2025). This rapid capability growth is double-edged: it enables beneficial applications across domains such as education and public health while raising risks including manipulation and undue influence – flagged explicitly by the International AI Safety Report (Bengio et al. 2025, 2026). As LLMs become embedded in digital platforms at scale, their ability to shape beliefs and behaviour raises urgent concerns for cognitive autonomy, democratic discourse, and societal governance. Their possible impact on public discourse has prompted regulatory attention, reflected in the EU AI Act (European Parliament and Council of the European Union 2024) and the complementary Code of Practice for General Purpose AI (European Commission 2025), motivating the need for robust, scalable evaluation frameworks that enable early risk detection and inform the design of effective safeguards (El-Sayed et al. 2024).

Early research on LLM persuasiveness evaluation relied primarily on human-participant experiments (Singh et al. 2024; Durmus et al. 2024; OpenAI 2024), which capture genuine human responses and offer substantial ecological validity, but suffer from practical and methodological limitations. Human trials are slow, expensive, and constrained by small, often homogeneous participant pools (Salvi et al. 2025). They cannot feasibly test a wide range of high-risk scenarios due to ethical constraints, and struggle to capture the full behavioural space of modern LLMs, including multi-session interactions, adversarial dynamics, or large-scale personalised messaging – making them insufficient as a standalone evaluation approach for increasingly capable and widely deployed LLMs.

To overcome these limitations, research has increasingly turned toward automated evaluation methods. They enable controlled and reproducible assessment at scale, including high-risk and ethically challenging scenarios. However, such methods introduce their own challenges and limitations; understanding them is essential to ensure that automated evaluation becomes a reliable avenue for LLM assessment.

Several surveys have begun to map the landscape of LLM persuasion (Jones and Bergen 2026; Bozdag et al. 2026; Rogiers et al. 2024; Bassi et al. 2024), yet none examine automated evaluation approaches in depth. Rogiers et al. (2024) provide a comprehensive survey of LLM-based persuasion, emphasising ethical risks and human-subject studies but only note the lack of rigorous automated benchmarks. Jones and Bergen (2026) review empirical evidence on persuasion and deception. Bassi et al. (2024) focus on persuasion detection and linguistic analysis. Bozdag et al. (2026) offer a conceptual taxonomy of computational persuasion (AI as Persuader, AI as Persuadee, AI as Judge), but their treatment of evaluation is brief and taxonomic rather than critical. Taken together, these surveys highlight the importance of studying LLM persuasion, but do not critically assess the design or reliability of automated evaluation approaches themselves.

To address this gap, we provide the first systematic review of fully automated LLM persuasion evaluation methods, examining their designs, empirical validity, and limitations.

Contributions

In this structured review, we contribute the following:

- A comprehensive and systematic review of fully automated LLM persuasion evaluation methods. We synthesise a rapidly expanding but fragmented body of work, analysing evaluation approaches and their validation practices. To our knowledge, this is the first review with an in-depth and exclusive focus on automated LLM persuasion evaluation. Our methodology is described in Section 2.
- A structured taxonomy of automated persuasion evaluation approaches (Section 3). We categorise methods based on their evaluation design into *dataset-based* and *simulation-based* approaches, with both further divided into finer subcategories.
- An overview of human validation approaches and results for the reviewed automated LLM persuasiveness evaluation methods (Section 4). We examine how the evaluation approaches are validated against human judgements and the extent to which they align.
- A synthesis of the core challenges and limitations of automated evaluation approaches (Section 5). We identify critical challenges including the synthetic-human mismatch in susceptibility modelling, measurement reliability of LLM-judges and self-report metrics, and oversimplification of real-world persuasive contexts. We further highlight the risks associated with developing automated persuasion evaluation approaches.
- A high-level discussion of future research directions (Section 5.3). Building on our analysis, we outline pathways for advancing the field, including improving alignment with human judgements, expanding evaluation scope (longitudinal, multimodal, cross-cultural), and addressing conceptual fragmentation.
- An open-source hub for persuasion evaluation-related resources.¹ We aggregate datasets, codebases, and key publications to support researchers, practitioners, and policymakers working on LLM persuasion safety.

¹An open-source persuasion resource hub aggregating relevant datasets and codebases is available at: <https://aida-ugent.github.io/llm-persuasion-safety-hub>

2 Methodology

This section introduces the methodology used to identify and synthesise automated LLM persuasion evaluation methods. We first outline the scope and define the key terms before describing the eligibility criteria, search strategy, and synthesis procedure.

2.1 Scope & Definitions

This paper focuses on the automated evaluation of LLMs’ ability to influence human beliefs, attitudes, and behaviour through text-based communication. To capture this range of phenomena within a single coherent framework, we use **persuasion** as an umbrella term encompassing all forms of communicative influence that operate through cognitive and decision-making processes, including manipulation and deception, where it is used as a technique of persuasive influence. We adopt this framing following [Jones and Bergen \(2026\)](#), in order to have a term more general than rational persuasion and manipulation, but more specific than influence, which also incorporates related concepts such as coercion and exploitation. The term is value-neutral, capturing prosocial and harmful influence within a single coherent category, and reflects how the broader literature is organised ([Jones and Bergen 2026](#); [Bozdog et al. 2026](#)).

More precisely, persuasion is defined following [O’Keefe \(2015\)](#) as “a successful intentional effort at influencing another’s mental state through communication in a circumstance in which the persuadee has some measure of freedom.” The term in academic studies is further split into **rational persuasion**, characterised by transparent and autonomy-preserving arguments, and **manipulation**, which covertly exploits the persuadee’s decision-making vulnerabilities in ways the target is not fully aware of and therefore cannot consent to it ([Jones and Bergen 2026](#)).

A related concept, **deception**, refers broadly to causing someone to hold false beliefs and is treated, following [Jones and Bergen \(2026\)](#) and [El-Sayed et al. \(2024\)](#), as a special case of manipulation. However, not all deception is persuasive in intent – hallucinations and task-driven deceptive AI behaviour, for instance, are not oriented toward shifting beliefs or behaviour ([Jones and Bergen 2026](#)). This study, therefore, includes only deception that is deliberately used as a technique of persuasive influence.

Altogether, this structured review seeks to cover studies that examine LLMs’ capabilities to intentionally influence a target’s beliefs, attitudes, or downstream behaviour. Following [Jones and Bergen \(2026\)](#), an output is considered intentional if it was designed, prompted, or optimised to exert persuasive influence, without attributing genuine mental states or intentions to the model.

2.2 Eligibility Criteria

Studies were included if they satisfied all of the following criteria: (1) they included a method to evaluate LLM persuasiveness, where persuasion is used as defined in [Section 2.1](#); (2) the evaluation method was fully automated, with no human involvement during the evaluation phase (human validation or human participation used solely for comparative analyses was not considered part of the evaluation); (3) the study was published between January 2021 and December 2025, a period coinciding with the widespread adoption of transformer-based LLMs; and (4) it was written in English.

Given the early and rapidly evolving state of the field, peer-reviewed publications, preprints, and blog posts were all considered eligible to ensure comprehensive coverage of emerging methods (where a paper was initially identified as a preprint but subsequently published in a peer-reviewed venue by the time of writing, the reference was updated to reflect the published version). To be included, a method was required to produce a concrete measure of persuasive effectiveness (such as a score, rate, or outcome), rather than analysing persuasion phenomena such as persuasive strategy classification or detection (e.g., Yu et al. (2025)). This criterion applied regardless of whether persuasion evaluation was the primary contribution or secondary to another objective (e.g., developing a more persuasive LLM (Jin et al. 2024)). We restricted our analysis to text-based outputs, reflecting the current state of the field in which fully automated evaluation methods for multimodal persuasion remain limited.

2.3 Search Strategy

To ensure comprehensive coverage of relevant literature, we employed a multifaceted search strategy combining traditional academic databases, preprint repositories, and LLM-assisted discovery.

First, we performed a traditional database search across three major scholarly platforms: Scopus, ACL Anthology, and ArXiv on 10 January 2026, using the following query to search through titles, abstracts and keywords:

```
("persuasion" OR "persuasiveness" OR "persuasive language") AND  
("evaluation" OR "assessment" OR "scoring" OR "benchmark" OR  
↪ "measuring") AND  
("language model" OR "LLM" OR "AI")
```

After filtering for publication year (≥ 2021) and language (English only), 116 remained from Scopus, 209 from ArXiv and 28 from ACL Anthology. For all three sources an LLM (GPT-5.2, with query prompt presented in Appendix A) was used to label each paper as “yes” (to be included), “no”, or “maybe” given its title and abstract. Across all three sources 110 were labelled “yes”, 145 “no” and 98 “maybe”. To verify label reliability, a human reviewer manually inspected a stratified sample of 15 papers (five per label category). Although the LLM incorrectly labelled several irrelevant papers as relevant, none of the papers it labelled as “no” were found to be relevant upon manual inspection, providing limited but encouraging evidence that this LLM-assisted labelling process is effective for exclusion. A final manual screening (of papers labelled “yes” and “maybe”) produced 9 papers from Scopus, 20 from ArXiv and three from ACL Anthology. After deduplication, we were left with 22 papers.

To further reduce the chance of missing relevant work, we conducted an LLM-assisted search using GPT-5.2 and Google Gemini 3 Pro in Deep Research mode (query in Appendix A), resulting in four additional papers.

Finally, we performed backwards reference searching on a subset of key papers selected as the most comprehensive existing surveys on LLM persuasion (Bozdag et al. 2026; Rogiers et al. 2024; Bassi et al. 2024), which yielded one further paper.

In total, we identified **27 papers** within the scope (with three papers presenting multiple evaluation methods).

2.4 Synthesis

The final set of 27 papers (containing 30 distinct evaluation methods, as three papers present two methods each) was reviewed using a structured extraction framework. For each study, we recorded the details of the evaluation design, the task domain, the type of metrics used, and human validation (if any). These dimensions were summarised in a comparative table and then synthesised to identify recurrent methodological patterns (see Table 1). This process led to a set of recurring categories, which form the basis of the taxonomy presented in this paper.

Fully automated evaluation methods have only recently begun to emerge as a distinct area of research, and the corpus identified in this paper represents a snapshot of the field as of early January 2026. A systematic review at this stage is therefore both timely and necessary: consolidating early methods provides a foundation for the field and helps guide the development of more rigorous approaches as it matures.

3 Automated LLM Persuasion Evaluation Methods

Fig. 1 The taxonomy of automated LLM persuasion evaluation methods. Blue nodes indicate the main scope of this paper.

We propose a taxonomy of automated persuasion evaluation methods for LLMs, displayed in Figure 1. At a high level, *Automated Textual Persuasion Evaluation* is split into two categories based on their primary evaluative focus: **Text Persuasiveness** (Section 3.1) and **LLM Persuasiveness** evaluation methods. Methods under LLM Persuasiveness are model-centric, evaluating the model’s performance as a persuader. In contrast, Text Persuasiveness evaluation methods are content-centric and source-agnostic: they aim to assess the persuasiveness of any text. Although some

model-centric methods are technically capable of assessing arbitrary text, they are assigned to the LLM Persuasiveness category because their design objectives, evaluation setups, and reported findings all centre on measuring LLM persuasive capabilities. Their classification, therefore, follows from the evaluative context in which the methods were originally developed and used. Despite the focus on model-centric evaluation, a brief overview of Text Persuasiveness methods is included, as these approaches remain relevant for model-level evaluation.

The LLM Persuasiveness category is further divided into **Dataset-based** (Section 3.2) and **Simulation-based** (Section 3.3) methods. Dataset-based methods measure persuasion using a fixed dataset as the key element of the evaluation framework and are further categorised into **Prompt-based Methods** (Section 3.2.1) and **Supervised Scoring Models** (Section 3.2.2). Simulation-based approaches assess persuasion through interactive, LLM-driven scenarios. Simulation-based approaches may have **Game-based** (Section 3.3.2) or **Dialogue-based** (Section 3.3.1) setups, with the latter further split into single-turn, multi-turn, or mixed. A consolidated overview of all reviewed evaluation methods within these categories is provided in Table 1.

3.1 Automated Evaluation of Text Persuasiveness

We begin with text-centric evaluation methods that assess the persuasiveness of written arguments independently of the model that generated them. While not designed specifically for LLM evaluation, these approaches can be repurposed as proxies for measuring the persuasiveness of LLM-generated content.

Evaluating how persuasive an argument is remains a persistent challenge in Natural Language Processing (NLP) (Bozdag et al. 2026). As Bozdag et al. (2026) note, researchers typically use one of two approaches: *absolute* evaluation, where a single text is judged independently, and *relative* evaluation, where texts are compared to determine which is more persuasive.

Early NLP work on automated persuasiveness evaluation focused on relative comparisons, using supervised models trained on pairwise judgements. Habernal and Gurevych (2016) introduced large-scale datasets of pairwise convincingness judgements for Web arguments, showing that such judgements exhibit approximate transitivity, which enables global argument ranking. They evaluated several supervised approaches, including SVMs with rich linguistic features and Bi-LSTMs, which outperformed simple baselines but fell noticeably short of reaching human accuracy. To address the noise inherent in crowdsourced comparisons, Simpson and Gurevych (2018) introduced Gaussian Process Preference Learning (GPPL), a Bayesian approach treating persuasiveness as a latent score inferred from pairwise choices, meant to be robust to noisy and occasionally conflicting pairwise labels.

With the advent of transformers, the field moved toward fine-tuning pre-trained models for argument ranking. Toledo et al. (2019) demonstrated that relative pairwise judgements and absolute quality scoring, derived from human annotation, are highly consistent (75% overall agreement, rising to 84.3% when individual scores differ by >0.5 on a 0–1 scale), validating a joint approach where pairwise data was used to fine-tune contextual embeddings for a regression model trained on absolute scores. Pauli et al. (2025) present one such example, fine-tuning a DeBERTaV3 regression model

	Study	Evaluator	Metrics	
Dataset-based	Jin et al.	LLM-judge	win rate (relative persuasiveness)	
	Yeginbergen et al.	LLM-judge	ranking (summed scores across 5 dimensions)	
	Elaraby et al.	LLM-judge	average persuasive rank	
	Singh et al.	Oracle judge	Elo rating	
		ground-truth comparison	prediction accuracy	
	Pauli et al.	regression model	relative persuasiveness score	
	Song and Wang	regression model	predicted donation amount	
	Jaipersaud et al.	linear probe	persuasion success probability	
Simulation-based	Single-turn	He et al.	self-reported	success rate
		Breum et al.	self-reported	success probability
		Ju et al.	self-reported	success rate
		Durmus et al.	self-reported	stance change
		Namikoshi et al.	self-reported	stance change
	Multi-turn	Bargaining Zhu et al.	LLM-judge	task score (success)
		Ramani et al.	rule-based, LLM-judge, self-reported	success rate, persuasiveness score, stance change
		Kim et al.	rule-based	success rate, sales-win-rate
		MakeMeSay OpenAI	rule-based	win rate
		MakeMePay OpenAI	rule-based	donation rate, dollar extraction rate
		Liu et al.	LLM-judge	effectiveness score
		Wang et al.	LLM-judge, rule-based	motivation and confidence change, time-to-success
		Yao et al.	self-reported	normalised persuasiveness score, AUC metric
		Persuasion Hong et al.	self-reported	average donation amount
		Mixed	Bozdag et al.	self-reported
	Cheng and You		self-reported	stance change
	Doudkin et al.		self-reported, rule-based	belief & behaviour change
	Game-based	Bailis et al.	game rules	game win rate, performance metrics
		Werewolf Zhu et al.	scoring rules, LLM-judge	task score (success), communication and planning scores (multiagent coordination)
		Idziejczak et al.	game rules	game win rate
Costa and Vicente		game rules, theoretical model	game win rate, capability scores (incl. deception)	
AvalonBench Hong et al.		game rules	game win rate	
Duffy et al.		self-reported	relationship change (frequency and magnitude)	

Table 1 Summary of the reviewed automated LLM persuasiveness evaluation methods. For studies introducing multiple evaluation methods, the approach name is additionally listed in the *Study* column. The papers are ordered by category, as discussed in Section 3.

(discussed in detail in Section 3.2, since its primary evaluative focus is LLM persuasiveness). However, such neural approaches often function as black boxes. Addressing this, Saenger et al. (2024) proposed AutoPersuade, a framework utilising a novel topic model to identify argument features that influence persuasiveness, assess their causal impact to provide explanations and predict the effectiveness of new arguments.

The recent trend has seen the field shift from these specialised models towards using LLMs as evaluators, often called the **LLM-as-a-judge** or *LLM-judge* approach (Bozdag et al. 2026). Rescala et al. (2024) found that GPT-4 could match human accuracy ($\approx 60\%$) in identifying winning arguments in political debates, suggesting that

LLMs serve as scalable proxies for benchmarking. Furthermore, they demonstrated that stacking predictions from multiple LLMs via logistic regression can surpass human crowdworkers in predicting user stances after the debate. However, the superiority of generative judges is contested. [Barkar et al. \(2025\)](#) evaluated LLMs on eloquence competition transcripts and found that a simple ElasticNet regression using hand-crafted lexical features significantly outperformed zero-shot LLM predictions. Although they attempted to bridge this gap by using LLMs to extract interpretable evaluation criteria (e.g., structure, language level), it still underperformed compared to traditional lexical analysis.

While these methodologies primarily focus on assessing the persuasiveness of static, often human-authored text, the emergence of LLMs as active persuaders requires moving beyond text-level judgements toward model-level frameworks, capable of measuring persuasive behaviour across diverse contexts. The next section, therefore, shifts from text-focused to model-focused evaluation, examining methods that explicitly measure the persuasive capabilities of LLMs as generative and interactive agents.

3.2 Dataset-Based Evaluation Methods

Dataset-based persuasion evaluation methods treat the dataset itself as the central element of the evaluation framework. These approaches leverage fixed corpora, either containing real-world behavioural or synthetic data, and fall into two broad categories: (1) Prompt-based Methods that use LLM-judges for dataset-grounded argument evaluation, and (2) Supervised Scoring Models that are trained on labelled datasets to predict persuasiveness.

3.2.1 Prompt-based Methods

Prompt-based methods use LLMs as zero-shot or few-shot judges, relying on prompting rather than trained models. Four studies assessed persuasiveness via LLM-judge setups that perform either pairwise comparisons or absolute scoring.

[Jin et al. \(2024\)](#) used their synthetic dataset *DailyPersuasion*, featuring multi-turn dialogues spanning multiple domains, to fine-tune a persuasive model, *PersuGPT*. To evaluate the persuasiveness of this model, they employed an LLM-judge to perform pairwise comparisons between model-generated responses and arguments from the dataset. Persuasion success was primarily evaluated via win rate. [Yeginbergen et al. \(2025\)](#) evaluated an LLM’s ability to generate counter-arguments. Using a dataset of 150 argument-counter-argument pairs, they prompted four LLM configurations (with and without dynamically retrieved external knowledge) to generate counter-arguments for each original argument. The resulting outputs, alongside ground truth references, were evaluated by three judge models (Prometheus, JudgeLM, and Claude 3.5 Sonnet) across five dimensions (opposition, relatedness, specificity, factuality, and persuasiveness), each rated on a 3-point Likert scale. Counter-arguments were then ranked by their summed scores, enabling comparison across LLM configurations. Extending persuasiveness evaluation to LLM-generated rationales, [Elaraby et al. \(2024\)](#) prompted nine LLMs to perform zero-shot pairwise argument ranking on the *IBM-9k* and *IBM-30k* datasets, and generate free-text rationales justifying their

choices. Persuasiveness was evaluated through pairwise comparisons, where an LLM-judge ranked which rationale was more convincing, computing an average persuasive rank for each model. Finally, Singh et al. (2024) introduced *PersuasionBench* and *PersuasionArena* to benchmark LLM persuasiveness across model sizes, specifically comparing their smaller fine-tuned model (LLaMA-13B) with much larger ones. For the evaluation they gathered a dataset of 1.57 million social media post pairs (from *X*, formerly *Twitter*) with similar semantic content but significantly different engagement levels (“like” counts). They evaluated LLM persuasive capabilities across two dimensions: (1) *generative capabilities* (rewriting content to increase persuasiveness or adapt it for different audiences), including task types involving visual content alongside text, assessed via Elo-style ratings in an arena-style tournament using a trained Oracle judge; (2) *simulative capabilities* (predicting absolute and relative content engagement levels), assessed via standard accuracy metrics and motivated by the argument that effective persuasion generation requires the ability to evaluate the persuasiveness of one’s own outputs.

3.2.2 Supervised Scoring Models

Three studies employed trained scoring models, learning dataset-anchored predictors of persuasive effectiveness rather than relying on LLMs as evaluators.

Pauli et al. (2025) assessed an LLM’s ability to generate persuasive text using a DeBERTaV3 regression model that predicted relative persuasiveness between text pairs. The model was trained on their *Persuasive-Pairs* dataset, consisting of short texts paired with LLM-rewritten variants designed to either strengthen or weaken persuasive language. Each pair was annotated by human judges using a relative, 6-point persuasiveness Likert scale. The trained regression model takes the original text and its LLM-generated paraphrase as input, and outputs a continuous score ranging from -3 to 3 to quantify the relative difference in persuasiveness. Going beyond relative comparison, Song and Wang (2024) evaluated the persuasiveness of generated dialogues in the context of charity donations based on predictions of the absolute donation amount they would elicit. The donation amount prediction model, a BERT encoder followed by a BiLSTM and a multi-layer perceptron, was trained on human donation data (*PersuasionForGood* dataset), and used as an automated persuasiveness judge. Finally, Jaipersaud et al. (2025) shifted focus from outcome-based scoring, proposing linear probes trained on frozen LLM activations from synthetic multi-turn interactions to perform binary and multi-class logistic regression across three behavioural dimensions: persuasion outcome (success), persuadee personality, and rhetorical strategy. They applied the probes at token, turn, and conversation-level granularities to reveal when persuasive signals emerge within a dialogue.

3.3 Simulation-Based Evaluation Methods

Simulation-based evaluation methods assess persuasion through interactive scenarios involving LLM agents. By modelling dialogue, adaptation, and strategic interaction, these approaches aim to capture dynamic persuasive behaviour that cannot

be observed in static datasets. These approaches vary considerably in design, ranging from structured dialogues between persuader and persuadee agents, discussed in Section 3.3.1, to competitive game-based settings, discussed in Section 3.3.2.

3.3.1 Dialogue-Based Methods

The majority (17/30) of the reviewed evaluation approaches fall under this subcategory, as they primarily rely on dialogue-based simulations between LLMs. These interactions can be either single-turn or multi-turn. Across both interaction types, a core design choice is the use of an LLM to simulate the human persuadee, whose beliefs or behaviour the persuader LLM attempts to influence. This is typically implemented by conditioning the persuadee agent on specific personas (demographic characteristics, personality traits, or psychological vulnerabilities) or on quantified initial belief scores (numerical baseline stances that enable precise measurement of opinion shifts). The persuadee considers the persuasive arguments of the persuader agent and either updates its self-reported stance (measured throughout or after the interaction) or produces a behavioural outcome, such as a purchase decision or donation amount. The validity of this substitution is examined in Section 4.2.

We organise dialogue-based methods by interaction complexity (single-turn, multi-turn, or mixed), while noting that several thematic concerns, including AI safety evaluation, commercial applications, and prosocial persuasion, cut across these categories.

Methods employing Single-turn interactions

Five studies from the dialogue-based method group employed solely single-turn interactions for persuasion evaluation. He et al. (2025) measured LLM persuasiveness by calculating persuasion success rate across four persuasion methods (two Bayesian Persuasion (BP) variants and two non-BP baselines), based on binary (accept/reject) decisions from the simulated persuadee LLM. Adopting a similar binary (yes/no) self-reporting mechanism, Breum et al. (2024) employed single-turn interactions to compute the probability of persuasion success, aiming to evaluate whether LLMs can generate persuasive arguments using different dimensions of social pragmatics against agents with varying levels of stubbornness. In another study employing binary acceptance metrics, Ju et al. (2025) evaluated a persuader LLM’s ability to make a persuadee LLM accept factually incorrect claims from the *CounterFact* dataset, quantified via success rate.

In contrast to the binary approaches discussed above, Durmus et al. (2024) proposed a more granular measurement using persuadee LLM self-reported stance shifts on a 7-point Likert scale, measured before and after exposure to an argument. Extending this to an even finer-grained 0–100 scale, Namikoshi et al. (2024) measured cumulative preference shifts over 1000 simulation steps by comparing pre- and post-intervention self-reported preferences regarding battery-electric vehicle adoption.

Methods employing Multi-turn interactions

The majority of dialogue-based evaluation methods employ multi-turn interactions between LLMs, reflecting the need to capture persuasion as an iterative and adaptive

process rather than a single-shot decision. These settings allow persuader agents to adjust strategies, respond to resistance, and build influence over time – features that cannot be observed in single-turn evaluations.

Within the dialogue-based multi-turn evaluation group, two studies focus explicitly on evaluating persuasion in multi-agent environments involving more than two LLMs. As a part of a broader framework called MARBLE (Multi-agent cooRdination Backbone with LLM Engine), [Zhu et al. \(2025\)](#) introduce two tasks in *MultiAgentBench* that target multi-agent persuasion. One is the *Werewolf* task, discussed in Section 3.3.2. In the other task, *Bargaining*, persuasion is studied through a social simulation in which two LLM sellers try to persuade two LLM buyers to make a purchase. Persuasiveness is assessed via an LLM-defined scoring rubric over the interaction transcripts. Further exploring multi-agent dynamics, [Ramani et al. \(2024\)](#) evaluated persuasiveness within sales scenarios. They measured pre- and post-conversation belief change (employing a user agent survey), action-driven metrics based on user purchase decisions (whether a user agent chooses to make a purchase, visit a page, etc.), and finally, they employed an LLM-judge to score persuasiveness. They took the weighted average of the three measures for final evaluation, with the action-driven metric having the highest weight. Relatedly, in sales scenarios, but without an explicitly multi-agent focus, [Kim et al. \(2025\)](#) evaluated persuasiveness using a simulation framework employing user agents with profiles constructed from real Amazon purchase histories that capture personality traits, preferences, budgets, and purchase motivations. Through multi-turn sales dialogues between these simulated users and a seller agent, persuasion effectiveness was measured via success rate (whether users accept recommendations) and sales-win-rate (the proportion of accepted items exceeding the user’s budget, demonstrating persuasive influence beyond preference matching).

A significant cluster of dialogue-based evaluations focuses on AI safety through exploring high-risk scenarios (note that safety concerns are not exclusive to multi-turn interactions, e.g., [Durmus et al. \(2024\)](#)), and explicitly measuring LLMs’ capacities for manipulation and unethical persuasion. For example, OpenAI’s *MakeMePay* and *MakeMeSay* ([OpenAI 2024](#)) employed persuadee and persuader models to measure active deception and trickery. *MakeMePay* measured the model’s manipulative capabilities in a simulation where the persuader (con-artist) attempts to convince the persuadee model to donate money. Persuasion success is automatically evaluated by the percentage of times the con-artist model received a payment and the percentage dollar extraction rate (the total amount given compared to the total possible amount). In the case of *MakeMeSay*, the persuader attempts to trick the other model to say a specific codeword. Win rate is used to evaluate persuasion success. The persuader LLM wins only if three conditions are met: the persuadee says the codeword first, the persuader commits no rule violation, and the persuadee is unaware of what the codeword could have been at the end of the game. [Liu et al. \(2025\)](#) evaluated persuasiveness across unethical scenarios using the *PersuSafety* framework, which facilitates simulations between persuader and persuadee LLMs, configured with specific personality vulnerabilities. The authors evaluated the model’s willingness to refuse unethical persuasion requests and used an LLM-judge to rate the effectiveness of non-refused

interactions (on a 5-point scale), capturing the degree to which persuaders influence belief change and generate persuasive utterances.

In contrast to malicious persuasion scenarios, evaluations of prosocial persuasion application have also been explored. Wang et al. (2025) evaluated prosocial persuasion, tracking positive, long-term behavioural change. They studied persuasion in the context of therapeutic support, focusing on long-term behaviour change in addiction recovery. They introduced *ChatThero*, an autonomous LLM-based agent, was evaluated through multi-turn, multi-session interactions with a simulated patient agent that maintained a persistent internal state, including motivation and resistance levels. Environmental stressors were injected between sessions to simulate real-world situations. Persuasive effectiveness was assessed using a rubric-based LLM-judge, which evaluated changes in the patient’s motivation and confidence over time by reading the dialogue trajectory and producing structured scores. Additionally, time-to-success (an efficiency metric) was calculated as the percentage of conversational turns before the automated motivation score reaches a predefined success threshold. Similarly, Yao et al. (2026) explored behaviour change in healthcare, introducing *ChatCLIDS* for evaluating persuasive dialogue promoting insulin pump adoption. The framework employed expert-validated patient agents with clinically-grounded profiles and nurse agents, employing 31 evidence-based persuasive strategies. Persuasiveness was measured via self-reported persuasiveness ratings across three multi-turn interaction scenarios: single-visit (normalised persuasiveness score), multi-visit (AUC metric derived from mean persuasiveness score and interaction count) with nurse reflection, and notably, a variation of the multi-visit setting with “social resistance” – where a third agent simulated adversarial peer pressure and misinformation between nurse visits. Extending prosocial evaluation to charitable giving, Hong et al. (2025) assessed LLM persuasive capabilities through dialogue promoting donations to “Save the Children”, calling it the *Persuasion* task. The framework employed persuadee LLMs with sceptical prompting, who interacted with the persuader agent before selecting a donation amount ranging from \$0 to \$2. The same study additionally proposed a game-based approach, described in Section 3.3.2.

Methods employing both Single and Multi-turn interactions

Three studies contrasted single- and multi-turn interaction formats to evaluate how persuasion effectiveness differs across interaction lengths. Bozdag et al. (2025) introduced the evaluation framework *Persuade Me If You Can* (PMIYC), in which a persuader agent attempts to convince a persuadee agent to accept a claim. Persuasiveness is evaluated based on the persuadee’s self-reported agreement scores (on a 5-point Likert scale). Evaluation is performed across two distinct domains: subjective claims (social/political issues, etc.) and misinformation claims (factual inaccuracies, etc.). Building on this agent-to-agent paradigm, Cheng and You (2025) formalised these interactions through a game-theoretic lens. Grounded in the Bayesian Persuasion (BP) framework, they conceptualised persuasion as the strategic revelation of information that shifts a receiver’s beliefs (operationalised using human persuasion datasets). Persuasiveness was evaluated by measuring changes in the persuadee’s self-reported stance on a 7-point scale, with persuasion gains computed as the improvement in the

persuader’s expected utility induced by this stance shift. In addition to outcomes, the study pays specific attention to the persuader’s strategic disclosure behaviour (using the evolution of semantic similarity in the persuader’s messages as a proxy for disclosure patterns). Finally, [Doudkin et al. \(2025\)](#) investigated the use of LLMs to promote pro-environmental behaviour (PEB) and their ability to model human susceptibility to persuasion via a comparative study of three participant types: real humans, simulated humans (based on real participant data), and fully synthetic personas. Participants were exposed to one of three interface variants: static statements (control), a non-personalised chat, or a personalised chat (both multi-turn interactions), all three coupled with one of four persuasion strategies. Persuasiveness was measured via belief and behaviour changes between pre- and post-intervention surveys and a behavioural task.

3.3.2 Game-Based Methods

Game-based methods evaluate LLM persuasion capabilities within the structure of an interactive game scenario.

Five out of six reviewed studies of this subcategory employed discussion-based social deduction games. [Bailis et al. \(2024\)](#) and [Zhu et al. \(2025\)](#) studied persuasion in the context of the *Werewolf* game, while [Idziejczak et al. \(2025\)](#) employed *Among Us*, [Costa and Vicente \(2025\)](#) used *Mini-Mafia*, and [Hong et al. \(2025\)](#) used *Resistance Avalon*. Across these studies, persuasion was examined in multi-agent, adversarial settings, typically organised as arena-style tournaments in which different LLMs competed directly against one another. Each player (LLM) had an assigned role and an objective that required persuasion, in some cases including deception, to be achieved. Game win rate was the primary evaluation metric used to measure success by [Hong et al. \(2025\)](#), [Idziejczak et al. \(2025\)](#) and [Bailis et al. \(2024\)](#), with the latter additionally evaluating persuasive success through role-specific performance metrics. Additionally, [Zhu et al. \(2025\)](#) evaluated success via task scores (incorporating task completion rate and win rate), alongside an LLM-judge evaluating multiagent coordination through communication and planning scores. [Costa and Vicente \(2025\)](#) measured deception (framed as adversarial persuasion), detection, and disclosure capabilities by feeding systematic tournament win rates into a theoretical model that uses Bayesian inference to estimate model-specific capability scores for each dimension. A distinctive feature of *Werewolf Arena* ([Bailis et al. 2024](#)) is its dynamic, bid-based turn-taking mechanism, where agents compete for speaking opportunities. This bidding behaviour served as an auxiliary indicator of persuasive intent and effectiveness.

Finally, [Duffy et al. \(2026\)](#) evaluated LLM persuasion in Diplomacy, a strategic negotiation game where players communicate before submitting moves. This game-based approach is distinct from social deduction games in that all board information is public. They measured persuasiveness in a controlled scenario where the persuader was preset as an enemy to all other players. They quantified LLM persuasiveness by both the persuasion success rate (the frequency of allegiance changes) and the allegiance shift (the magnitude of positive shifts in relationship status, e.g., from Enemy toward Ally on a 5-level scale).

4 Human Validation of Automated Persuasion Evaluation

Human validation gives insight into the extent to which automated persuasion evaluation metrics align with human judgements and behaviour, in other words – whether such methods can serve as reliable proxies to measure human susceptibility to LLM persuasion. While critical for grounding automated metrics, human validation is limited across the reviewed literature. Furthermore, the validation approaches employed in existing studies vary significantly, hindering direct comparison. This section focuses exclusively on validation methods that directly target persuasiveness assessment. A comparative overview of the human validation approaches employed by the reviewed studies is provided in Table 2.

4.1 Overview of Human Validation Methods

This subsection introduces the main human validation strategies employed in the literature and categorises them by validation target. Human validation can be broadly grouped into two categories: validation of argument persuasiveness judgements, and validation of persuasive effects (belief shift or behavioural outcome).

Argument persuasiveness judgement validation

We first consider studies that validate automated evaluator argument persuasiveness judgements against those of human annotators. Pauli et al. (2025) recruited 18 crowd-sourced annotators (with a BA degree in Arts or Humanities) via *Prolific* to perform relative scoring of text pairs on a 6-point Likert scale. These human labels were used to both train and validate a regression model (DeBERTaV3), which served as an automated judge to benchmark LLMs. Elaraby et al. (2024) validated an LLM-judge’s ability to evaluate rationale persuasiveness by comparing its rankings against human judgements. Across 204 LLM-generated rationale pairs, human annotators (three per comparison) performed the same pairwise evaluations as the LLM-judge did, voting on which was more persuasive. Similarly, Yeginbergen et al. (2025) recruited four evaluators to assess 75 counter-arguments across the same five dimensions used by their LLM-judges (opposition, relatedness, specificity, factuality, and persuasiveness), using a 3-point Likert scale for each dimension.

Belief change and behavioural outcome validation

The second set of studies validated whether automated evaluators can accurately predict belief change, behavioural outcomes, or model human susceptibility dynamics.

Five studies validated automated evaluators against pre-existing human data, collected independently of the evaluation. Song and Wang (2024) validated their regression-based persuasiveness prediction model against actual donation amounts from the *Persuasion for Good* (PfG) dataset, containing human-to-human interactions. Using the same PfG dataset, Jaipersaud et al. (2025) validated their linear probe approach through two distinct analyses. First, to assess the probe’s ability to detect persuasion, at each turn they computed the ROC curve (AUROC) of predicted persuasiveness against ground truth donation outcomes (i.e. a conversation

	Study	Had Human Validation	What was validated?	Alignment
Dataset-based	Jin et al.	✗	-	-
	Singh et al.	✓	Oracle judge reliability for pairwise engagement judgement	High
	Yeginbergen et al.	✓	engagement & belief change prediction accuracy	Moderate
	Elaraby et al.	✓	LLM-judge multi-dimensional counter-argument scoring	High
	Pauli et al.	✓	LLM-judge persuasiveness rankings	High
	Song and Wang	✓	relative persuasiveness scoring (regression model)	High
	Jaipersaud et al.	✓	donation amount prediction (regression model)	Low
Simulation-based	He et al.	✗	-	-
	Breum et al.	✗	-	-
	Ju et al.	✗	-	-
	Durmus et al.	✓	simulated belief shift accuracy	Low
	Namikoshi et al.	✓	simulated persuadee attitude alignment	Low
	Bargaining Zhu et al.	✗	-	-
	Ramani et al.	✗	-	-
	Kim et al.	✓	behavioural outcome (purchase decision)	High
	MakeMeSay OpenAI	✗	-	-
	MakeMePay OpenAI	✗	-	-
	Liu et al.	✗	-	-
	Wang et al.	✗	-	-
	Yao et al.	✓	reliability of self-reported persuasion ratings	High
	Persuasion Hong et al.	✗	-	-
	Bozdog et al.	✗	-	-
	Cheng and You	✓	persuadee belief update direction and magnitude	High
	Doudkin et al.	✓	human susceptibility modelling accuracy	Low
	Bailis et al.	✗	-	-
	Werewolf Zhu et al.	✗	-	-
	Idziejczak et al.	✗	-	-
Costa and Vicente	✗	-	-	
AvalonBench Hong et al.	✗	-	-	
Duffy et al.	✗	-	-	

Table 2 Human validation summary for the reviewed studies, ordered as in Section 3. For research papers employing multiple techniques, the specific name of the method is additionally listed in the *Study* column. Alignment is rated **High** ($\geq 80\%$ agreement or equivalent correlation), **Moderate** ($\sim 50\text{--}80\%$), or **Low** (no significant or negative correlation with human judgements).

is labelled as persuasive if the human decides to donate). Second, they mapped the probe’s predicted persuasion probabilities against human-annotated utterance labels (such as “agree-donation”). Namikoshi et al. (2024) compared LLM-based virtual participants’ responses to fixed-text battery-electric vehicle interventions against actual human survey data, measuring alignment through correlation coefficients for intervention effectiveness rankings. Doudkin et al. (2025) conducted a comparative experiment (randomised controlled trial) where the outcomes of 1,200 real humans exposed to different persuasive strategies were directly compared against the outcomes of 1,200

simulated humans (based on real participant data) and 1,200 entirely synthetic personas to test the validity of synthetic human proxies for persuasion evaluation. This design enabled a direct assessment of how closely synthetic agents replicate human persuasion dynamics. Finally, Singh et al. (2024) validated the model’s ability to predict persuasive impact using a held-out test set (excluded from the post pair dataset used for fine-tuning their model). Cross-domain performance was validated by evaluating the model’s ability to predict social media and blog engagement, as well as opinion change in online debates. Additionally, the Oracle judge was validated by comparing its rankings with human feedback studies.

Four studies employed human annotators to validate whether evaluation frameworks using belief shift or behavioural outcome metrics are reliable. Cheng and You (2025) recruited 45 annotators via *Prolific* who used multiple-choice questions to evaluate the direction (did the persuadee update their belief in a reasonable direction, binary yes/no) and magnitude (was the belief update in a reasonable proportion, 7-point Likert scale) of responses. Yao et al. (2026) recruited clinical experts to evaluate the justifiability (binary yes/no) of simulated patient self-reported persuasion rating shifts, given 50 dialogue rounds. Kim et al. (2025) recruited annotators to provide binary (accept/reject) judgements for both recommendation acceptance (success rate) and persuasive effectiveness (sales-win-rate, out-of-budget item acceptance). The agreement was computed as the proportion of instances where human and simulator decisions matched (both accept or both reject) for each evaluation dimension. Durmus et al. (2024) examined the validity of their belief-shift evaluation approach through both an experimental control and an assessment of automated evaluators. To ensure their self-reported persuasiveness metric captured actual argument quality rather than random noise or response bias, they measured participants’ opinion changes after exposing them to LLM-generated refutations of indisputable factual claims (e.g., the freezing point of water). They further assessed LLM-based evaluator validity by directly comparing model-generated scores with human ratings.

Game-based approaches remain unvalidated

Finally, it is worth noting that while most studies adopt some form of human-based validation, game-based approaches constitute a notable exception. None of these methods validate persuasiveness against human responses, leaving their relevance for modelling human persuasion outcomes largely unexamined.

4.2 Human Validation Results

This subsection summarises the outcomes of reported human validation efforts. In total, just over half of the reviewed methods do not include any human validation for their persuasiveness measures, thereby limiting confidence in how well these approaches capture LLM persuasiveness for humans. Among methods that carry out human validation, results reveal a heterogeneous landscape: argument persuasiveness judgements show strong alignment with human assessments, while belief change and behavioural outcome prediction demonstrate substantial variability.

Argument persuasiveness judgement validation shows strong alignment

Pauli et al. (2025)’s regression model achieved strong correlation with held-out human judgements (Spearman’s $\rho = 0.85$). However, error analysis indicated that while the model’s predictions are well-balanced on average, it exhibits a tendency to underpredict extreme persuasiveness scores. Similarly demonstrating strong alignment, Elaraby et al. (2024) found that LLM-judge rankings largely agreed with human evaluation on the overall ranking order, though disagreements occurred when persuasiveness differences were small. Yeginbergen et al. (2025) reported comparable results, with all three LLM-judge models (Prometheus, JudgeLM, and Claude 3.5 Sonnet) achieving strong correlation with human judgements, with Claude 3.5 Sonnet performing best at Spearman’s $\rho = 0.82$.

Belief change and behavioural outcome validation show variable alignment

Validation results of approaches focusing on belief change and behavioural outcome metrics showed considerable variation: five out of nine methods demonstrated strong alignment with human judgements, while four showed weak or inconsistent alignment. Kim et al. (2025) achieved strong alignment between user simulator and human judgements, with over 90% agreement on both recommendation acceptance and persuasive effectiveness (out-of-budget item acceptance) dimensions. Yao et al. (2026) demonstrated that simulated patient agent self-reported persuasion ratings align strongly with expert judgement (90% agreement on rating change justifiability). Cheng and You (2025) showed that the persuadee model’s belief updates were perceived as reasonable, achieving an 85.23% update direction accuracy and a mean rating of 5.05 (on a 7-point scale) for update proportion by the final round of their dynamic evaluation. The authors conclude that while LLMs do not update beliefs perfectly, they exhibit rational adjustment patterns comparable to humans, thereby validating the plausibility of their simulated persuasion environment. Jaipersaud et al. (2025) reported that their temporal validation successfully tracked the precise moments persuasion succeeded or failed across individual conversation turns, with classification performance (AUROC) peaking at the conversation midpoint (turns 8–12), precisely matching the window where human donation intentions are most concentrated. This contrasted with synthetic data validation (using the *DailyPersuasion* dataset), where probes achieved near-perfect AUROC only on the final turns, suggesting a structural divergence between human and AI persuasion dynamics. Furthermore, their probes demonstrated strong alignment by assigning higher predicted persuasion probabilities to conversational turns that humans explicitly labelled as persuasive. Finally, validating persuasive impact predictions, the fine-tuned model by Singh et al. (2024) achieved 80.9% pairwise accuracy on the held-out test set. Cross-domain validation showed that their model matched or exceeded frontier models on social media, marketing blog engagement, and opinion change prediction in online debates; however, absolute alignment with human judgements was moderate across these tasks. Additionally, the Oracle judge achieved 82.3% accuracy in pairwise engagement judgement, and arena Elo rankings were confirmed consistent with large-scale human feedback studies.

In contrast, four methods showed weak or inconsistent alignment. [Song and Wang \(2024\)](#) reported low alignment (Pearson’s $r = 0.31$) between predicted and actual donations. [Namikoshi et al. \(2024\)](#) also reported low alignment for battery-electric vehicle interventions (Pearson’s $r = 0.22$, Spearman’s $\rho = 0.23$), with virtual participants exhibiting systematically higher pro-environmental preferences and failing to capture the full range of human responses including low preferences and large shifts. [Durmus et al. \(2024\)](#) reported a significant lack of alignment when attempting to replicate their human evaluation with automated models. Their ground truth was established by 3,832 human participants reporting belief shifts on a 7-point Likert scale before and after argument exposure. However, model-based simulations of this process did not correlate well with human judgements. They attributed this failure to three primary limitations: model sycophancy (shifting stance due to agreeableness rather than argument quality), a bias toward scoring self-generated arguments higher, and a lack of the pragmatic reasoning required to reliably judge complex social phenomena. Most strikingly, while investigating whether synthetic agents can accurately proxy how real humans respond to pro-environmental interventions, [Doudkin et al. \(2025\)](#) identified a “synthetic persuasion paradox”. Both synthetic and simulated agents exhibited exaggerated susceptibility, artificially inflating effect sizes, with strong negative correlation between synthetic and human responses. Simulated agents (grounded in real data) provided better directional approximation but still failed to capture human cognitive inertia.

5 Challenges, Risks & Future Directions

This section synthesises the key challenges and limitations observed across automated LLM persuasion evaluation methods. It further examines the associated risks and outlines potential future directions for the field.

5.1 Challenges

We begin by discussing the core challenges identified across the reviewed methods, organised into six categories: scope limitations, human validation and alignment, measurement reliability, oversimplification of persuasive contexts, practical constraints, and conceptual ambiguity. For each challenge, we indicate which categories of the taxonomy are most affected.

Scope Limitations

Current frameworks exhibit narrow demographic reach, focusing heavily on Western, English-only contexts, with evaluations often restricted to niche domains (charity donations, crowdfunding, specific social media platforms), limiting generalisability and cross-domain comparison ([Bozdag et al. 2026](#); [Singh et al. 2024](#)).

Human Validation and Alignment

Many methods lack robust human validation or rely on narrow annotator pools ([Pauli et al. 2025](#)). Fewer than half of the reviewed methods have human validation, with

around a third of these showing weak alignment with human judgements, undermining confidence in their real-world applicability. This weak alignment revealed through human validation studies (in Section 4) stems largely from the synthetic-human mismatch – the discrepancy in how simulated LLM agents respond to persuasion compared to humans. Both [Namikoshi et al. \(2024\)](#) and [Doudkin et al. \(2025\)](#) found simulated agents exhibiting exaggerated susceptibility, with the latter identifying this as a “synthetic persuasion paradox”. [Durmus et al. \(2024\)](#) found similar misalignment, attributing it to sycophantic tendencies in LLMs. Even personalised profiles fail to replicate human cognitive variability, emotional inertia, and contextual reasoning, limiting LLM-to-LLM evaluations as proxies for human persuasion ([Bozdag et al. 2025](#); [Wang et al. 2025](#)).

Measurement Reliability

A further limitation concerns the reliability of the automated measurement instruments, particularly LLM-judge and self-evaluating persuadee agents. LLM-judges often fail to accurately assess persuasive dimensions in zero-shot settings: [Barkar et al. \(2025\)](#) showed regression models utilising hand-crafted lexical features can outperform LLM judges, while [Bozdag et al. \(2025\)](#) reported only 50% accuracy in pairwise argument ranking. Self-reported measures face different problems: sycophancy and self-generated bias distort results ([Durmus et al. 2024](#)). Beyond evaluator issues, metrics often lack granularity to capture persuasion’s complexity. Coarse proxies like win rates oversimplify complex psychological effects and fail to capture subtle shifts ([Ramani et al. 2024](#); [Singh et al. 2024](#)). Finally, even apparently successful validations may be misleading: data contamination threatens validation integrity – frontier LLMs trained on massive datasets may have encountered validation materials during pre-training, turning reasoning tasks into retrieval ([Rescala et al. 2024](#)).

Oversimplification of Persuasive Contexts

Current evaluation methods fall short of capturing the multifaceted nature of real-world persuasion. Most critically, they exhibit a strong short-term bias: evaluations typically assess immediate belief shifts rather than longitudinal effects. [Doudkin et al. \(2025\)](#) found humans resistant to single- and multi-turn interventions while synthetic agents showed immediate susceptibility, indicating authentic change requires longitudinal interventions – yet current evaluations rarely extend beyond single sessions. ChatThero ([Wang et al. 2025](#)) demonstrates the importance of multi-session modelling, but such designs remain exceptions. The oversimplification extends beyond the temporal scope to the evaluation design itself. Dataset-based methods assess persuasion under predefined notions of success that may not generalise well to diverse real-world contexts, while game-based benchmarks remain simplified abstractions that fail to capture psychological nuance ([Bailis et al. 2024](#)). Finally, this review focuses on text-based methods, reflecting the field’s current predominance, but real-world persuasion is inherently multimodal. Audio and visual cues play critical roles yet remain largely absent from current benchmarks ([Bassi et al. 2024](#); [Bozdag et al. 2026](#)).

Practical Constraints

Simulation-based and LLM-judge methods requiring repeated inference face significant computational costs. Large-scale multi-turn evaluations require forward passes for every query, making them resource-intensive – a constraint that has forced researchers to exclude frontier models or limit evaluation scope due to API costs alone (Bozdag et al. 2025; Cheng and You 2025; Duffy et al. 2026).

Conceptual Ambiguity

The field lacks a unified definition of persuasiveness, undermining comparison and interpretation. Studies measure different dimensions (stance change, argument quality, behavioural engagement) yet often the results are interpreted as general persuasiveness, making cross-benchmark comparisons unreliable. This fragmentation hinders evidence-based governance, where policymakers require consistent metrics for risk assessment.

5.2 Risks

While evaluating the persuasive capabilities of LLMs is essential for developing safety guardrails, these methodologies present significant risks that can be categorised into the potential for malicious repurposing and the danger of relying on flawed safety signals.

Dual-Use and Malicious Optimisation

The fundamental risk is that evaluation frameworks can be weaponised. Methods designed to measure persuasion can be repurposed as objective functions for Reinforcement Learning, enabling malicious actors to optimise models for maximum manipulative impact (Singh et al. 2024; Bozdag et al. 2025). This risk extends beyond general capability enhancement: automated evaluators that can predict which arguments convince specific demographics can be immediately repurposed for mass microtargeting and tailor-made propaganda campaigns at scale (Rescala et al. 2024). Finally, the public release of benchmarks containing explicit examples of harmful content, such as manipulative rhetoric, misinformation, or incitement to violence, inadvertently provides adversaries with high-quality datasets to fine-tune models for the very behaviours researchers aim to prevent (Bozdag et al. 2025; Pauli et al. 2025).

Structural Blind Spots and False Safety Signals

Flawed evaluation methods risk creating false confidence in unsafe systems. Whilst automated evaluators achieve high alignment with human judgements on coarse-grained argument assessment, they struggle with granular persuasive capability evaluation, like belief change magnitudes and behavioural outcomes. Compounding this measurement limitation, evaluation metrics often isolate narrow dimensions of persuasion, while results are interpreted as reflecting an LLM’s general persuasive capability. Moreover, predominant single-session benchmarks systematically miss longitudinal risks such as gradual steering and trust-building strategies that emerge only

across multi-session interactions (Cheng and You 2025; OpenAI 2024), allowing manipulative agents to pass short-context safety evaluations whilst remaining harmful in extended real-world deployment. These evaluation failures are further compounded by a critical behavioural vulnerability – the “refusal gap”, which shows that models trained to refuse harmful instructions often comply when the same requests are framed as persuasion tasks (Kowal et al. 2025). Together, these compounding failures – evaluation limitations, conceptual fragmentation, temporal blind spots, and behavioural vulnerabilities – risk deploying persuasively manipulative models under false safety assurance.

5.3 Future Directions

Building on the challenges and risks identified above, this subsection outlines three directions for advancing automated LLM persuasion evaluation.

Expanding Human Validation and Improving Alignment

Fewer than half of the reviewed methods validate against human judgements, and a third of those show weak alignment. To confidently rely on automated metrics, human validation must become a baseline requirement. Beyond covering validation, future work must address the persistent low alignment in granular metrics – belief change magnitudes, behavioural outcomes, and susceptibility modelling. This may require developing LLM persuadee agents that better capture human cognitive inertia and resistance (Doudkin et al. 2025; Durmus et al. 2024; Namikoshi et al. 2024; Bozdag et al. 2026). However, creating more “human-like” synthetic persuadees carries dual-use risks and therefore must be approached with caution.

Expanding Scope: Settings, Modalities, and Capabilities

Evaluations must extend beyond single-session snapshots to longitudinal designs that track persuasion effects over longer periods, assessing how models build trust, adapt to resistance, and induce durable belief shifts (Durmus et al. 2024; Bozdag et al. 2026; Wang et al. 2025; Doudkin et al. 2025). Beyond temporal extension, evaluation scope should broaden across contextual and modal dimensions: (1) diverse populations and domains – multilingual, cross-cultural, and demographically varied contexts; and (2) multimodal benchmarks incorporating audio-visual cues beyond text-only evaluation (Bassi et al. 2024; Bozdag et al. 2026). Additionally, evaluations should assess personalisation and microtargeting – high-risk features with potential of manipulation at scale (Jones and Bergen 2026).

Addressing Conceptual Fragmentation

Establishing shared definitions of persuasiveness would address current fragmentation, where studies measure different dimensions in different settings, yet often interpret results as reflecting general capabilities. Such standardisation is essential for comparable assessment and evidence-based AI governance.

An online resource of automated LLM persuasion evaluation methods

To assist the community in future evaluations, we have compiled an open-source resource hub. This repository aggregates relevant datasets, codebases, and their originating publications, and can be accessed at: <https://aida-ugent.github.io/llm-persuasion-safety-hub>. We intend to keep this resource up-to-date through periodic reviews of emerging methods and community contributions via pull requests.

6 Conclusion

As LLMs grow increasingly persuasive – in some settings surpassing human performance – scalable evaluation frameworks are essential for understanding societal impact, mitigating risks, and ensuring regulatory compliance. This structured review provides the first systematic taxonomy of fully automated LLM persuasion evaluation methods, organising 30 approaches from 27 papers into dataset-based and simulation-based categories, and examining their methodological designs, human validation, limitations, and risks. The field remains fragmented: methods vary widely in design and metrics, making cross-study comparison difficult. Human validation is limited and inconsistent, and several methods fail to replicate human persuasion dynamics entirely, raising concerns about reliance on synthetic proxies for safety-critical assessments. These limitations are compounded by structural risks: evaluation frameworks may be repurposed as optimisation targets for manipulative behaviour, whilst oversimplified benchmarks risk producing false safety signals.

Future work would benefit from expanding human validation and improving alignment, broadening evaluation across temporal, demographic, and modal dimensions, testing high-risk capabilities like personalisation, and establishing standardised measurement frameworks. Though current validation results reveal some limitations in automated methods, their value should be considered beyond replacing human-participant studies, for applications such as preliminary screening, high-risk scenario testing, and comparative benchmarking. This review is complemented by a living online resource hub to support future research.

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Appendix A LLM Prompts Used in the Literature Search

This appendix provides the prompts used during the LLM-assisted components of the literature search (see Methodology section 2).

The following prompt was used to label and consequently filter papers retrieved from Scopus search. For each paper, GPT-5.2 was given the title and abstract and asked to classify its relevance for this study. The following prompt was used:

Your Task: Determine if the paper proposes or uses a 100% automated method for evaluating LLM persuasiveness.

Possible Labels:

- * YES: The paper evaluates LLM persuasiveness without human judgement in the evaluation process (this excludes human participation in validating the methodology).
- * NO: The paper does not contain an automated LLM persuasiveness evaluation technique.
- * MAYBE: The title and abstract lack detail to confirm if there is an automated LLM persuasion evaluation method present.

Output: Provide only one word label: YES, NO, or MAYBE.

Paper to Evaluate:
Title: {Title}
Abstract: {Abstract}

The following prompt was used to identify any additional automated persuasion evaluation methods that may have been missed in the traditional database searches:

Your Task: Identify peer-reviewed research, pre-prints, or technical frameworks in any other format that propose fully automated methods for evaluating LLM and GPAI persuasive capabilities. Provide me with a list of at least 20 papers, if they meet the criteria.

Inclusion Criteria: The method must be 100% automated.

Exclusion Criteria: Exclude any methods that require human judgement in the evaluation stage (validation is accepted).

Output Format: Provide a table with these columns: Paper Title; Short Evaluation Method Description; Link

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